

Covid-19 Vaccination of Children

Intention of healthcare workers to get their children vaccinated against Covid-19

* Required

1. If you are a healthcare employee (at any designation) and have child/children below 18 years of age, you are invited to participate in this web-based online survey. This is a research project titled "**To understand the perception of Health care workers about their intention to get their children vaccinated against Covid-19.**" This being a voluntary participation, you may refuse to take part in the research or exit the survey at any time without any penalty. All the information shared shall be kept absolute confidential. Please click on YES below to provide your consent and continue to participate in this study. Your participation is of utmost value. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 2*

No

Sociodemographic characteristics and past medical history

2. Your contact number.

3. Your age in completed years *

4. Gender *

Mark only one oval.

Male

Female

Prefer not to say

5. Religion *

Mark only one oval.

Hindu

Muslim

Sikh

Christian

Other

6. Highest level of Education *

Mark only one oval.

Illiterate

Up to Primary

High school

10+2 or equivalent

Graduate

Post-graduate

PhD/DM

7. Department *

8. Designation *

Mark only one oval.

- Faculty member
- Resident doctor
- Nursing Officer (OT, OPD, Vaccination)
- Pharmacist
- OPD/Ward/Lab Attendant
- Technician (Nonmedical)
- Sanitary attendant/Housekeeping staff
- Engineer
- Security Guard
- Other

9. Type of Employment *

Mark only one oval.

- Permanent
- Contractual
- Short project/ Tenure

10. Marital status *

Mark only one oval.

- Currently married
- Divorced
- Widow/Widower

11. Locality Background *

Mark only one oval.

Rural

Urban

12. Per capita income in INR (Total family income of all members from all sources divided by number of family members) *

Mark only one oval.

<10000

10000-50000

50000-100000

>100000

13. Are you suffering from any chronic illness? (any disease more than 3 months) *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 14*

No *Skip to question 15*

Chronic illness

14. Chronic illness

Self covid-19 history

15. Have you ever tested positive for Covid-19? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 16*

No *Skip to question 17*

Hospitalization

16. Did you require hospitalization? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Self Covid-19 Vaccination

17. Self Covid-19 Vaccination status *

Mark only one oval.

Received 2 doses and one booster dose *Skip to question 18*

Received 2 doses only *Skip to question 18*

Received single dose only *Skip to question 18*

Not vaccinated *Skip to question 20*

Adverse effects of Covid-19 vaccine?

18. Did you experience any adverse/side effect after receiving the COVID-19 vaccine? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 19*

No *Skip to question 20*

Management of adverse effects of Covid-19 vaccine

19. Did you require..... for adverse effect following Covid-19 vaccination ? *

Mark only one oval.

- OPD consultation
- Hospitalization
- None of these

The primary source of information about the COVID-19 vaccine.

20. The primary source of information about the COVID-19 vaccine.(can tick multiple option) *

Check all that apply.

- Traditional Media (Television, Radio and Newspapers)
- Social and online media (WhatsApp, WeChat, Facebook, Twitter and Internet news)
- Workplace
- Family and friends

Details of children

21. How many child do you have *

Mark only one oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3 or >3

22. Total no. of children between 12-17 years and their gender

Check all that apply.

	Male	Female
Child 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Child 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Child 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

23. Have any of your child tested positive for COVID-19 in past? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes *Skip to question 24*

No *Skip to question 26*

Child tested Covid-19 positive

24. Did the child require hospitalization due to COVID-19? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

25. What was outcome? *

Mark only one oval.

Recovered

Post-covid syndrome

Died

Vaccination of children

26. Have u got any of your child aged 12 years and above vaccinated for COVID-19? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, all child/children vaccinated
- Yes, only male child/children vaccinated
- Yes, only female child/children vaccinated
- None

27. Have you vaccinated your child with mandatory childhood vaccines? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Covid-19 Vaccine Hesitancy Scale (VHS)

The scores can range between 1 and 5, with higher scores indicating higher COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy

[Five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly agree, 2 = agree, 3 = neither agree nor disagree, 4 = Disagree, 5 = strongly disagree)].

28. COVID-19 vaccines are important for child's health. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

29. COVID-19 vaccines are effective. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

30. Having COVID-19 vaccination is important for the health of others in my community. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

31. COVID-19 vaccines offered by the government programme in my community are beneficial. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

32. COVID-19 vaccines carry less risks than other vaccines. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

33. The information I receive about the COVID-19 vaccines from the vaccine program is reliable and trustworthy. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

34. Getting the COVID-19 vaccines is a good way to protect my kid from disease. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

35. I will do what experts recommends about the COVID-19 vaccines. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

36. I don't think COVID-19 vaccines causes serious adverse effects. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

37. COVID-19 vaccines are needed though the Covid-19 is not common anymore. *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neither agree nor disagree
- Disagree
- Strongly disagree

Covid-19 vaccination status of child.

38. If you haven't yet get your your child vaccinated, would you do so in future... *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes *Skip to question 39*
- No *Skip to question 40*
- Can't say *Skip to question 40*

Will vaccinate your child

39. When you are planning to do so? *

Mark only one oval.

- As soon as possible
- After some time

Unwilling to get your child vaccinated.

40. If you don't want to get your child vaccinated, what is/are the reason/s? *

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